

Original Article

Research and Development, Remittances and Economic Growth: Evidence from Developing Countries

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Abstract

This research tries to find the relationship between R&D and economic growth, remittance and economic growth and the joint impact of R&D and remittance on the economic growth. The study analyzed the data of 52 developing countries and used the fixed effects technique. The findings confirmed that education is the most significant factor, highlighting the importance of building a skilled workforce to support economic progress. Similarly, R&D and remittances are significant individually as they play a crucial role in boosting economic growth, as it encourages innovation and brings advancement in technology, which helps in promoting economic performance. The joint impact of R&D and remittances is also significant and positive on economic performance. Alongside R&D, remittance and education, results revealed that trade openness and controlled inflation also plays a crucial role for fostering a stable economic environment

Keywords: R&D, remittances, economic growth, developing countries

INTRODUCTION

The concept of economic growth has been in highlights and has become one of the most researched concepts and evolved economic thoughts. Economic growth is a process where the quantity of goods produced, and services provided are higher than in the previous period and it promotes overall well-being of a country. It helps countries, especially developing countries, to transform them by elevating the living standards of residents, excess to better healthcare facilities and better education. It also reduces unemployment by creating more employment opportunities with the creation of new businesses and increased investment locally as well as internationally (Kreishan, 2011).

Higher economic growth also ensures the rise in tax collection which ultimately raises the government development expenditures due to which the level of human development influences positively (Tahir & Azid, 2015). Thus, achieving higher economic growth is considered in literature as the final objective of all economic activities as it is both directly as well as indirectly related to improved quality of life. Therefore, the question “what really causes higher economic growth?” has drawn a lot of attention in the literature from the policymakers, government authorities and researchers.

Being multidimensional economic growth is indeed a complex process which includes both internal factor like R&D, human capital, labour force and institutional quality (Islam et al., 2024a) and external factor like remittances, foreign aid and inflows of FDI (Tahir et al., 2019a). Endogenous growth theory also

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highlights the importance advancement of technology in result of R&D investments for sustainable and qualitative economic growth Yazgan & Yalcinkaya (2018).

Alongside R&D, remittances also have a significant role in the development of economies. It acts as a source of income that enhances consumption, encouraging investments, development of new businesses, creating employment opportunities and provide financial assistance to R&D spending in developing nation Zardoub & Sboui (2023). Remittances increase consumption, saving and investment and provide finance to government for the payment of import bills, it also helps in boosting the growth process through investment in human and physical capital (Meyer & Shera (2017). Cazachevici et al. (2020) the importance of remittance is evident from World Bank data that it has increased from \$641 billion in 2017 to \$843 billion in 2020 in which developing countries receive 74% of the global remittance. Remittances are the primary source of income for some countries and surpasses the FDI and foreign income Yadeta & Hunegnaw (2022). Further, remittance not only flows towards the small/developing economies, but it also flows to the developed countries like Germany, France, Belgium etc. are also among the top recipient of remittance.

Despite the importance of both R&D and remittances in economic development of a country, the combined effect of remittance and R&D on economic progress has not received enough attention, especially to developing countries. Keeping in view the importance of R&D and remittances on economic progress, many nations are seeking to increase and attract remittances and FDI. The correlation of remittances and R&D expenditures is complicated, as R&D helps in enhancing the exiting technology, innovations, productivity, and transforming human capital, while, remittance, provide financial resources for the R&D, increase the consumption, saving, investment and impacts positively to the balance of payment of a country, which ultimately stabilize the economy (Islam et al., 2024a; Siddique et al., 2012a). Although researchers such as (Bird & Choi, 2020a; Feeny et al., 2014; Siddique et al., 2012b; Sobiech, 2019a; Zardoub & Sboui, 2023) have examined effect of remittances on economic growth and others like (Afonso, 2016a; Chawla, 2020a; Inekwe, 2015; Jones, 1995; Mansfield, 1972; Sokolov-Mladenović et al., 2016) explore the effects of R&D on economic growth, studies on the joint impact of R&D and remittance remain rare. The long-run sustainable and permanent economic progress dependent on technological advancement and R&D investments Yazgan & Yalcinkaya (2018).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Siddique et al. (2012) revealed that remittance is turning to be a crucial provider for external income to these countries. Feeny et al. (2014) used data from 1971-2010 paying special attention to Small Island Developing States (SIDS). He found that remittances play a crucial role in SIDS economic growth as remittances account for more than 25 percent of SIDS GDP and 90 percent of households are remittance receivers and SIDS thus requires establishing and improving the policies employed by other countries.

Remittances are crucial for supporting families and its inclusion in SDGs further emphasize its importance globally. Sobiech (2019) conducted a study on 61 emerging countries using data over 1970-2010 and concluded that remittances strongly affect the economic growth of countries with weak financial system but negatively affect the financial system. It also results in reducing poverty in short-run and beneficial for financial segment in long-run. It also suggests that policies are needed to attract more inflow of remittance and highlights that further research is needed, which also includes the institutional quality. Bird & Choi (2020) conducted a study on 51 developing nations from 1976 to 2015 to analyze the impact of remittance, FDI and foreign aid and found that remittance has no substantial or a negative effect on the economic progress, moreover, in short- to medium-term remittance hinders economic growth. He concluded that strategies are needed for better and optimum impacts of combination of remittance, FDI and foreign aid strategies for sustainable development and comparative advantage.

For developing countries, remittance is essential source of revenue which provides better education, medical facilities, uplifting the living standard and providing foreign exchange for the payment of debts and import bills. Tahir et al. (2019b) conducted a study on SAARC using data from 2008-2015 and concluded that different factors affect economic growth differently. The suggested policies for managing brain drain and attracting FDI for sustainable economic growth.

Saha (2021) conducted research on Bangladesh's economy between 1995 and 2015 utilizing time series data concluded that remittance boosts the economy significantly and much greater in long-run. Study revealed that domestic investment further helps the economic development in long-term and the impact may be for greater than recorded due to undocumented remittances.

R&D and Economic Performance

R&D spending serves a pivotal role in the economic expansion of a country as it contributes towards the improvement and development of new technologies and innovation, modification of the existing techniques of production and services, and development of human capital. Samimi and Alerasoul (2009) concluded that countries who are leading the innovation and are involved more in R&D initiatives have a greater rate of economic progress than the others. Consequently, it is advised that administrations of developing nations should finance more R&D activities for the economic growth of their country.

Chawla (2020) conducted research on 18 OECD countries taking the data from 1981 to 2012 using fixed-effects panel regression and FGLS. The study reveals the convergence pattern among the 18 OECD countries due to investment in R&D investments during period under observation. Due to consistent investment in R&D across OECD countries, South Korea has managed to rise from 16 rank in 1981 to rank 1 in 2011. The study also reveals that UK, USA, Japan, France and Germany are the key R&D player among the 18 OECD nations during the timeframe with the share of 84.10% of total R&D investment.

Afonso (2016) conducted a study in 10 innovative countries to find association among the intensity of R&D, economic development and firm size growth using horizontal R&D endogenous-growth model. His study highlighted that with innovation complexity increases, R&D process becomes more labour intensive and requires more skilled and educated labour. These complexities also affect the diffusion of designs, due to coordination, organizational setups, rise in transportation cost and the magnitude of the markets. It was also concluded that initially the growth of the country slows down due to innovation, but with R&D remaining productive, the growth process again reaches a consistent and stable path, which shows positive correlation between R&D expenditure and economic growth.

To explore the role of R&D in European Union, Sokolov-Mladenović et al. (2016) conducted research for the period of 2002 to 2012 by employing multiple regression models, fixed-effects model and Hausman test. The study's finding emphasizes that even in the condition of financial crises, investment in R&D has positive effects on economic development. Results suggested that with the 1% increase in R&D investment results in 2.2% increase in the GDP. The findings of the investigation emphasize that the economic growth of a country boosts up with the increase in investment in R&D expenditures. Thus, making R&D spending a significant driver for economic development of a country.

Since technological transformation positively affects economic growth hence investigating the significance of R&D investments in the economic progress of a nation becomes more important. Guloglu & Tekin (2012) considering the worth of R&D investment for the economic development of country, conducted an empirical study to analyze the casual association between R&D investments, innovation and economic development of 13 high income along with highest ration of R&D expenditure OECD nations. By using Panel fixed effects and GMM on the data between 1991 to 2007 it was concluded that R&D spending and innovation, R&D spending and economic development and economic development and innovations are positively related to each other. The results of the study imply that investment in R&D triggers more spending in R&D activities which in turns boosts the growth of OECD countries.

Pala (2019) conducted investigation on 25 developing nations, using data from 1996-2016 by employing Random coefficient model (RCM) explored that R&D spending lead to the drop in performance. Moreover, Iran, Mexico, Tunisian, and Uzbekistan also have an adverse impact on economic progress however, some positive effects of R&D were also found for China, Ukraine, Russia and Turkey. The positive relation shows that these countries are utilizing their research efficiently, and R&D spending are in line with nations' need and demand.

Remittances, R&D and Economic Growth

Le & Bodman (2011) conducted research on 50 underdeveloped nations using the data from 1990 to 2000. By employing pooled least square methods the researchers discovered that labour from many developing nations migrated to the developed nations, where they are exposed to advanced technologies and get latest knowledge. Additionally, they also transfer these advanced technologies and latest knowledge to home countries, which contributes to innovation and increase productivity. Moreover, these migrant also transfer funds which provide the necessary finance required for investment and positively affect economic development. Overall, the study's findings highlighted that R&D's spending have directly affected economic development and remittance though have a smaller but direct impact on the economic development. Moreover, economic development of a nation is positively affected by both R&D spending and remittance.

Though R&D and remittance are important in dealing with the shortage of resources and elevating the poverty of the country, very few studies could be found in literature which have studied the joint impact of both factors on economic progress, especially regarding developing nations. Islam et al. (2024b) conducted a study to investigate the effect of R&D investments and remittances on the economic growth of middle-income countries (MIC). 25 MIC were considered for the study, using the data between 1996 to 2021. To analyze the data, panel ARDL and FGLS and results verified through D-H causality check. The results show that not only remittance and R&D have beneficial effect on economic progress individually, but the combined effect of these factors also found to be positive. The results also indicated two-way causative association amongst R&D spending, remittance and economic development. Results of the study concluded that R&D and remittance positively affect economic advancement and as economic progress increases the R&D spending and inflow of remittance also increases, which shows that R&D, remittance and economic progress are positively correlated. The suggestion presented by the study is, developing countries' governments should adopt policies for boosting the inflow of the remittance, which not only helps in the rise of the foreign currency but also provides the finance required for the R&D investments.

By reviewing the literature, it can be assumed that the R&D spending and inflow of remittance not only individually effects the economic growth positively but also significantly affects the economic advancement of a nation jointly. It is also evident from the review of literature that studies related to the association among R&D spending, remittance and economic advancement remain very scarce. Particularly the joint impact of R&D and remittance on economic growth specifically for the underdeveloped nations need to be explored. Therefore, our study will focus on how R&D investments and remittance influence the economic growth individually, and up to what extent R&D and remittance jointly impacts the developing countries' economic growth.

METHODOLOGY

The Model Development

This paper is conducted to see the association between R&D expenditures, remittance and economic progress of developing countries. To ensure robustness, additional variables including education, trade, inflation rate and investment are incorporated in the model. The below mentioned econometric model adopted for achieving the goal of this paper.

$$growth_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 R\&D_{it} + \beta_2 remit_{it} + \beta_3 edu_{it} + \beta_4 trade_{it} + \beta_5 inv_{it} + \beta_6 inf_{it} + \beta_7 R\&D_{it} \times remit_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

For finding the association among the R&D expenditures and economic advancement, remittance and economic advancement and joint impact of R&D spending and remittance on economic advancement of the evolving countries, we are therefore considering following 52 developing countries. Data is gathered from WDI from 2000 to 2023. The details of variables are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables

“Variables”	“Details”	“Source”
$growth_{it}$	“The growth rate of GDP per capita”	“WDI”
$R\&D_{it}$	“R&D expenditures as percentage of GDP”	“WDI”
$Remit_{it}$	“Personal remittances received as percentage of GDP”	“WDI”
edu_{it}	“Gross enrollment ratio at secondary level”	“WDI”
$trade_{it}$	“Trade as percentage of GDP”	“WDI”
inv_{it}	“Gross fixed Capital formation as percentage of GDP”	“WDI”
inf_{it}	“The growth rate of consumer price index”	“WDI”

Estimation Techniques

To estimate the relationship among the variables concerned, the study used the fixed effects. This research conducted the Hausman (1978). The test confirmed the use of fixed effects estimation.

RESULTS

Descriptive Discussion

Data provided in Table 2 shows wide variation of GDP among countries (369.84 to 21478.82) which shows the difference between industrialization, productivity and trade. Saudi Arabia and Oman are among the highest GDP countries while Congo and Dem. Rep, Madagascar have the lowest GDP. Data shows an average of 5.591 of GDP for Remittances. Some countries such as Tajikistan rely heavily on remittance while some countries like Iraq are receiving very low remittance. Generally, R&D spending in developing countries is very low but China has the highest percentage of R&D spending and Madagascar has very little spending. Trade openness relative to GDP averages to 76.923. However, the statistics show that the trade openness varies greatly due to different policies adopted by different countries. Country like Brazil, Argentina and Pakistan have restricted their trade while Malaysia and Viet Nam have extremely open towards trade.

Investment across countries also varies greatly. Countries like Armenia and Mongolia are investing aggressively while Tajikistan is investing the least. The rate of inflation also varies widely with the highest inflation of 59.219% and deflation of -10.067%, showing diversity. Education level also varies greatly with Costa Rica showing highest enrollment while Burkina Faso and Pakistan have lowest enrollment.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics

	GDP	REM	RD	OPEN	INVS	INFL	EDU
Mean	5804.011	5.591	0.424	76.923	22.407	6.164	85.611
Maximum	21478.82	44.126	1.912	220.406	46.833	59.219	141.202
Minimum	369.840	0.003	0.012	24.319	6.295	-10.067	10.102
Std. Dev.	4268.361	7.429	0.331	32.103	6.094	6.534	20.477

Regression Results

The data of 52 developing countries from 2000 to 2023 is analyzed using FEM and results are shown in Table 3. From Table 3, it is apparent that education (LNEDU) is the most significant factor with a high coefficient of 0.665 and p-value of 0.000, making it statistically significant. Results indicate that improvement in education has a positive effect on economic progress and countries who have better

educational systems have produced more skilled labour with great innovative potential. This highlights that policies need to be made for investing and supporting education which results in the economic expansion of the nation. The importance of R&D is evident from the result which shows coefficient of 0.285 and a low probability of 0.000. Through investing in innovation, technology, and new ideas, efficiency can be enhanced and gaining competitive advantage. Results suggests that supporting R&D is vital for achieving economic progression.

Positive but moderate impact of trade (LNOPEN) on GDP, which is reflected by a coefficient of 0.177 and the probability of 0.003. countries who have access to global market benefit from advanced technologies, better market efficiency and increased competition. Besides the fact that its impact is not as strong as education and R&D, trade still helps in economic development and suggests that enhancing trade through better policies can be beneficial. The positive impact of Remittance on economic growth is shown by coefficient of 0.074 and p-value of 0.000. Remittances help the residents, encourage investment and lift consumption. Furthermore, the results for interaction between R&D and remittance show a direct effect on the economic development of a country. With a coefficient of 0.067 and p-value of 0.020, indicating that when remittance is invested for the R&D, the combine effect of R&D and remittance on GDP is positive.

The coefficient of -0.002 along with p-value of 0.056 highlights that inflation (INFL) has a slight adverse effect on GDP. The results suggest that rise in general prices, purchasing power reduces, which creates uncertainty for the businesses and hinders the economic growth of a country. Although this effect is marginal. However, its impact is less significant when compared to education or R&D. Investment (LNINV) shows a very small positive coefficient of 0.036 showing no direct effect of investment on the GDP. Though the result suggests that investment may not have direct effect but it depends on other variables which are not included in the analysis.

The analysis shows that education, R&D, and trade are the major factors which influence economic development and positively support the growth process. Remittance has direct impact on economic development, especially when combined with R&D, the combined effects of both enhances growth. The findings of this model emphasize the importance of such policies which are focused on investing on education and R&D activities, supporting and becoming part of global trade will support in attaining the sustained economic growth.

The R-square value is 0.967, which shows that the model employed explains about 96.7% of the variation on GDP, thus proving that the model is robust.

Table 3. Regression Results

“Variables”	“Parameters”	“Sd. Errors”	“T-score”
LNEDU	0.665	0.054	12.178
LNINV	0.035	0.056	0.631
LNOPEN	0.177	0.060	2.948
INFL	-0.002	0.001	-1.907
RD	0.284	0.036	7.888
LNREM	0.074	0.015	4.933
RD*LNREM	0.067	0.029	2.326
Constant	4.407	0.430	10.235
R²:	0.967		
Adjusted R²:	0.964		

CONCLUSION

This research tested the relationship between R&D, remittance and growth of 52 developing countries from the data gathered from WDI for 2000 to 2023. A combination of statistical methods is used which includes descriptive statistics and regression analysis.

The findings of the results show there is a direct correlation between education and GDP, thus indicating that the economic performance of countries who invest more in educating the residents and have higher education level is much stronger than countries who are spending little on education. It further emphasizes that education is a critical factor which helps in the formation of better human capital, thus concluded that countries with higher levels of education experience higher productivity, have more innovation and are more capable of absorbing new technology and latest knowledge.

R&D play a role in the development of new technologies, innovation and increasing overall productivity and give competitive advantages over other countries. It has a positive relationship with economic development. Results indicated that developing countries who focus on R&D can reduce their dependency on imported technologies. It further showed the adaptability of industries and support diversification. It also creates a culture of technological progress and creativity.

The study also revealed that remittances play crucial for developing countries in lifting the living standards of the residents, approach to better health facilities and better education, provide funds to government for the payment of its import bills. The results show that due to the high dependency of countries on remittance masks the weak area of the countries that hinders the economic growth of these countries. Results of the study further highlighted that R&D and remittance not only have a positive effect on economic growth individually, but the joint impact of R&D and remittance is also positive. This synergy of R&D and remittance highlights the need of policies for encouraging migrants for investing in new businesses, trade, transfer of new technology and latest knowledge which ultimately promote performance. Similarly, the results also show significant and positive impact of trade on GDP. Trade openness attracts foreign investment as well as access to the global markets which benefits with the exchange of ideas and technologies which are essential for development of countries. For investment the results show statistically insignificant and positive effect on GDP, which shows that alone investment may not affect economic progress. However, with the combination of other factors like R&D, it may significantly affect economic growth. Countries need to focus and employ such policies which help in controlling the inflation and maintain the price stability and support economic growth.

REFERENCES

- Afonso, O. (2016a). R&D intensity, economic growth and firm-size growth: theory and practice. *Applied Economics*, 48(32), 2973–2993. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2015.1133896>
- Bird, G., & Choi, Y. (2020a). The effects of remittances, foreign direct investment, and foreign aid on economic growth: An empirical analysis. *Review of Development Economics*, 24(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/rode.12630>
- Blanco, L. R., Gu, J., & Prieger, J. E. (2016). The impact of research and development on economic growth and productivity in the U.S. States. *Southern Economic Journal*, 82(3), 914–934. <https://doi.org/10.1002/SOAJ.12107>
- Cazachevici, A., Havranek, T., & Horvath, R. (2020). Remittances and economic growth: A meta-analysis. *World Development*, 134, 105021. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2020.105021>
- Chawla, D. (2020a). Economic growth and R&D expenditures in selected OECD countries: Is there any convergence? *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, 12(1), 13–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20421338.2019.1608694>
- Feeny, S., Iamsiraroj, S., & McGillivray, M. (2014). Remittances and economic growth: Larger impacts in smaller countries? *The Journal of Development Studies*, 50(8), 1055–1066. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2014.895815>
- Guloglu, B., & Tekin, R. B. (2012). A panel causality analysis of the relationship among research and development, innovation, and economic growth in high-income OECD Countries. *Eurasian Economic Review*, 2(1), 32–47. <https://doi.org/10.14208/BF03353831>
- Hausman, J. A. (1978). Specification tests in econometrics. *Econometrica*, 46(6), 1251. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1913827>
- Inekwe, J. N. (2015). The contribution of R&D expenditure to economic growth in developing economies. *Social Indicators Research*, 124(3), 727–745. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-014-0807-3>
- Islam, M. Z., Rahaman, S. H., & Chen, F. (2024a). How do R&D and remittances affect economic growth? Evidence from middle-income countries. *Heliyon*, 10(9), e30160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e30160>
- Jones I. Charles. (1995). R & D-Based models of economic growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 103(4), 759–784.
- Kreishan. (2011a). Economic growth and unemployment: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(2), 228–231. <https://doi.org/10.3844/jssp.2011.228.231>
- Le, T., & Bodman, P. M. (2011). Remittances or technological diffusion: which drives domestic gains from brain drain? *Applied Economics*, 43(18), 2277–2285. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00036840903153838>
- Mansfield, E. (1972). Contribution of R&D to economic growth in the United States. *Science*, 175(4021), 477–486. <https://doi.org/10.1126/SCIENCE.175.4021.477>
- Meyer, D., & Shera, A. (2017). The impact of remittances on economic growth: An econometric model. *Economia*, 18(2), 147–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econ.2016.06.001>
- Pala, A. (2019). Innovation and economic growth in developing countries: Empirical implication of Swamy's random coefficient model (RCM). *Procedia Computer Science*, 158, 1122–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.252>
- Romer, P. M. (1986a). Increasing returns and long-run growth. *Journal of Political Economy*, 94(5), 1002–1037.

- Saha, S. K. (2021). The impact of remittance on economic growth in Bangladesh. *Scholars Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 9(9), 462–470. <https://doi.org/10.36347/sjahss.2021.v09i09.013>
- Samimi, A. J., & Alerasoul, S. M. (2009). *R&D and economic growth: New evidence from some developing countries*. Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences.
- Siddique, A., Selvanathan, E. A., & Selvanathan, S. (2012b). Remittances and economic growth: Empirical evidence from Bangladesh, India and Sri Lanka. *Journal of Development Studies*, 48(8), 1045–1062. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2012.663904>
- Sobiech, I. (2019a). Remittances, finance and growth: Does financial development foster the impact of remittances on economic growth? *World Development*, 113, 44–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.08.016>
- Sokolov-Mladenović, S., Cvetanović, S., & Mladenović, I. (2016). R&D expenditure and economic growth: EU28 evidence for the period 2002–2012. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 29(1), 1005–1020. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2016.1211948>
- Solow, R. M. (1988). Growth theory and after. *The American Economic Review*, 78(3), 307–317.
- Tahir, M., & Azid, T. (2015). The relationship between international trade openness and economic growth in the developing economies. *Journal of Chinese Economic and Foreign Trade Studies*, 8(2), 123–139. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCEFTS-02-2015-0004>
- Tahir, M., Estrada, M. A. R., & Afridi, M. A. (2019a). Foreign inflows and economic growth: An empirical study of the SAARC region. *Economic Systems*, 43(3–4), 100702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecosys.2019.100702>
- Yadeta, D. B., & Hunegnaw, F. B. (2022). Effect of international remittance on economic growth: empirical evidence from Ethiopia. *Journal of International Migration and Integration*, 23(2), 383–402. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12134-021-00833-1>
- Yazgan, S., & Yalcinkaya, Ö. (2018). The effects of research and development (R&D) investments on sustainable economic growth: Evidence from OECD countries (1996-2015). *REVIEW OF ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVES*, 18(1), 3–23.
- Zardoub, A., & Sboui, F. (2023). Impact of foreign direct investment, remittances and official development assistance on economic growth: panel data approach. *PSU Research Review*, 7(2), 73–89. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PRR-04-2020-0012>